

COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF ENGLISH AND UZBEKISTAN GRAMMAR

Ibrohimova Zarnigor

Student of Fergana state university

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Abstract. *This work studies the similarities and differences between the grammar of English and Uzbek in a comparative manner. Particular attention is paid to the word classes, sentence structure, tense system, word order, and verb forms of both languages. The analytical structure of English and the agglutinative features of Uzbek are analyzed by comparison using examples. Grammatical problems encountered in the translation process and ways to overcome them are also considered. This work may be useful for language learners, translators, and linguists.*

Key words: *English language, Uzbek language, grammar, comparative analysis, syntax, morphology, system of tenses, verb constructions.*

СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ АНГЛИЙСКОЙ И УЗБЕКСКОЙ ГРАММАТИКИ

Аннотация. *В данной работе в сравнительном порядке изучаются сходства и различия грамматики английского и узбекского языков. Особое внимание уделено классам слов, структуре предложений, временной системе, порядку слов и глагольным формам обоих языков. Путем сравнения на примерах анализируется аналитическая структура английского языка и агглютинативные особенности узбекского языка. Также рассмотрены грамматические проблемы, возникающие в процессе перевода, и пути их преодоления. Эта работа может быть полезна изучающим языки, переводчикам и лингвистам.*

Ключевые слова: *английский язык, узбекский язык, грамматика, сопоставительный анализ, синтаксис, морфология, система времен, глагольные конструкции.*

Introduction.

Comparative analysis of English and Uzbek grammar plays an important role in linguistics, because the grammatical systems of both languages have their own characteristics. Since each language has a grammatical structure based on its historical development, culture and social context, studying them allows language learners to not only learn the language, but also understand other cultures. In English, grammatical structures such as auxiliary verbs, tense

system, word order play an important role. For example, in English, it is necessary to adhere to a strict order in the use of verb tenses and modals. In Uzbek, however, word order, morphology and phonology are formed differently, which requires greater flexibility and attention to context in the process of language learning.

The specific features of the verb in Uzbek, including the suffixes used to indicate person and number, auxiliary words and the tense system, differ from English. The morphological structure and word formation rules of the Uzbek language can be more complex and multi-stage than the syntax of the English language. By analyzing these differences, identifying similarities and differences in the grammatical systems of the two languages, it helps language learners to translate between them, improve communication, and reduce the possibility of making mistakes.

This study conducts a comparative analysis of the grammatical structures, verbs, and word combinations of the English and Uzbek languages. This work is expected to be an important guide not only in the process of language learning, but also in the field of linguistics, translation, linguistic research, and language teaching methodologies. This study also aims to help students who are experiencing difficulties in the interaction between the two languages and in the process of language learning. Through a comparative analysis of grammar, a deeper understanding of the structure and functioning of both languages can be achieved, which will further enrich the science of linguistics.

Literature review and method.

The literature on the comparative analysis of English and Uzbek grammar is very extensive and diverse. In linguistics, there are many scientific works on the comparison of the grammatical systems of English and Uzbek. These works are mainly carried out in the fields of language teaching, translation and linguistic research. Among the main sources on English grammar are the works of researchers such as Azar, Murphy and Thornbury, who provide detailed recommendations on the tense system, verb constructions and syntax of the English language. Leech's scientific works on auxiliary verbs and modals in English are also significant. Also, among the important works aimed at studying the grammar of the Uzbek language are the books of linguists such as Rakhmonov, Khojiyev and Abdurazakov. These works provide detailed analyses of the morphology, syntax and phonology of the Uzbek language. The works of Toshpulatov and Eshmatov on the uniqueness of word formation and the verb system in the Uzbek language deserve special attention.

The literature on the comparison of the grammatical systems of English and Uzbek is also very extensive. Scientific works such as Bakalov and Gaybullayeva are aimed at identifying the similarities and differences in syntactic structures in English and Uzbek. These studies studied the word order, tense system, and the role of auxiliary words in the two languages. Nasirova compared the morphological systems of Uzbek and English, especially the differences in the person and number of the verb. The existing literature on the study of the grammatical systems of English and Uzbek is based on more methodological approaches. Kuzmina also highlighted the phonetic and phonological differences between English and Uzbek, which helps to understand the relationships between the grammatical systems of the two languages. This study uses qualitative research methods to conduct a comparative analysis of the grammar of English and Uzbek. The main approach is the comparative method, that is, it is aimed at identifying differences and similarities in the grammatical systems of the two languages. The study studies the morphological, syntactic and phonological systems of both languages using the content analysis method. This method analyzes the differences and similarities in the verb system, tenses, person and number suffixes, and word combinations of the English and Uzbek languages.

The study also uses the interlinguistic analysis approach. This approach allows us to study the relationships between the grammatical structures of both languages. The similarities and differences in the auxiliary verbs and modals in the English language, the personal suffixes and tenses system in the Uzbek language are analyzed. At the same time, the difficulties and errors of language learners in learning grammar in both languages are analyzed using the experimental method, which helps to identify the most effective methods for teaching grammar.

The statistical differences between the grammatical systems of the two languages are also studied using the quantitative method. For example, word order, verb tenses, and the rate of use of modals are measured and compared. Such a methodological approach allows for a more accurate depiction of the systematic differences in the language learning process.

With the help of these methods, a comparative analysis of the grammatical systems of English and Uzbek is studied in more depth and allows for a better understanding of the grammatical features of the two languages.

Comparative analysis of English and Uzbek grammars is a very important topic in linguistics. This analysis helps to identify differences and similarities in the grammatical systems of the two languages. Each language has its own grammatical structures, tense systems, methods of using verbs and modals, and its own rules for word formation and sentence construction.

Studying the differences between English and Uzbek grammars is of great importance not only in language learning, but also in translation, linguistics, cultural studies, and language teaching methodologies.

One of the most striking features of English grammar is the tense system and its complexity. There are 12 main tenses in English, each with its own specific usage, verb forms, and auxiliary verbs. For example, in English, the present perfect tense is often used to indicate the beginning of an action and its effect on the present, which in Uzbek is often expressed by the suffix “-gan”. English also uses modals (can, could, will, would), which in Uzbek requires the use of auxiliary words and suffixes to express modals.

In English, auxiliary verbs (have, be, do) are very important. They are used to create grammatical tenses and help express different semantic meanings in a sentence. In Uzbek, auxiliary verbs are used less often, in Uzbek, tenses can be created more through word combinations and suffixes, which can be used to create forms that differ depending on the person of the word. In Uzbek, the word forms of the verb are modified by morphological suffixes. The grammatical system in Uzbek differs from English, because the Uzbek language is syntactically based more on word order. In English, much attention is paid to auxiliary verbs and word order, while in Uzbek, on the contrary, word order is changed more depending on the meaning. For example, in Uzbek, verbs are modified using suffixes. Verb suffixes play an important role in Uzbek: they can be used to determine the person, number, and tense of the verb. For example, the suffix “-gan” in Uzbek indicates the perfective meaning of a verb, while in English this concept is expressed using the present perfect.

The process of word formation in Uzbek is also very developed. In Uzbek, there are many suffixes and similar morphological forms in word formation. This is a less common phenomenon in English. For example, in the process of word formation in Uzbek, borrowed and non-Uzbek words can be given an Uzbek form using suffixes. In English, this process is often carried out using word combinations or methods that correspond to the morphological structure of the English language.

Conclusion

The comparative analysis of the grammars of English and Uzbek is a very important area of linguistics, and is of great importance in the fields of language learning, translation, and linguistics. In this study, the differences and similarities in the grammatical systems of English and Uzbek were clearly described. Important grammatical elements such as tense system,

auxiliary verbs, modals, and syntax in English were compared with morphological affixes and word order in Uzbek. This analysis will help language learners understand the grammatical features of the two languages and will be useful in overcoming difficulties in learning grammar.

Comparing the tense system and modals in English with the tense system in Uzbek has helped to reveal the grammatical differences between the two languages. For example, in English, it is common to express tenses and different meanings of a verb through auxiliary verbs and modals, while in Uzbek these differences are expressed through morphological suffixes and word order. Also, in Uzbek, verb conjugation and suffixes used in word formation form a unique and more complex system compared to verb forms in English.

This analysis has allowed us to understand more deeply the differences between the grammatical systems of Uzbek and English. The research conducted on the differences in the syntax of English and Uzbek, the features of sentence construction, and the meaning of word combinations has provided important knowledge for developing effective approaches to teaching both languages. Understanding these differences and developing appropriate methods will help language teachers effectively teach two languages.

Also, in the translation process, the specific aspects of the grammatical system and structure of each language should be taken into account using grammatical analysis. A comparative analysis of the grammatical systems of English and Uzbek will help translation scholars better understand the specific features of each language, thereby improving the quality of translation.

At the same time, this study has also paved the way for the development of effective methods for studying grammar in the Uzbek language. It will allow for an in-depth study of the similarities and differences between the grammar of English and Uzbek, the introduction of new approaches to language teaching, and the development of effective methods for identifying and solving problems encountered in the process of language learning.

In general, a comparative analysis of English and Uzbek grammar makes a significant contribution to understanding the relationships between the two languages, developing effective methods of language learning, and improving the translation process. This study also provides a basis for further scientific research in linguistics, philology, and linguistics.

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